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THEORY & FACTORS AFFECTING JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Job satisfaction can also be seen within the broader context of the range of issues which affect an individual's experience of work, or their quality of working life. Job satisfaction can be understood in terms of its relationships with other key factors, such as general well-being, stress at work, control at work, home-work interface, and working conditions. A study titled "Analysis of Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction of the Employees in Public and Private Sector", in India concluded that in India Employees tend to love their job if they get what they believe is an important attribute of a good job. Weightage factor of each such attribute based on exhaustive survey has been calculated. Region, sector and gender wise study of job satisfaction has provided consistent picture with respect to distribution of data set analyzed showed that most of the employees in Indian industry are not satisfied with their job except for a few like male in commerce sector and female in education sector. Total job satisfaction level of males is found to be higher than that of woman. Total job satisfaction level in manufacturing sector is found to be very low.

KEY WORD: Theory, Factors, Job Satisfaction

WHAT IS JOB SATISFACTION:

Job satisfaction is not the same as motivation, although it is clearly linked. Job design aims to enhance job satisfaction and performance; methods include job rotation, job enlargement and job enrichment. Other influences on satisfaction include the management style and culture, employee involvement, empowerment and autonomous work groups, pay, work responsibilities, variety

of tasks, promotional opportunities the work itself and co-workers. Job satisfaction has been defined as a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job; an affective reaction to one's job; and an attitude towards one's job. Weiss (2002) has argued that job satisfaction is an attitude but points out that researchers should clearly distinguish the objects of cognitive evaluation which are affect (emotion), beliefs and behaviors. This definition suggests that we form attitudes towards our jobs by taking into account our feelings, our beliefs, and our behaviors.

DIMENSIONS OF JOB SATISFACTION:

According to the Luthan 2002, there are three generally accepted dimensions of job satisfaction.

1. Job satisfaction is an emotional response to a job situation.
2. Job satisfaction is often determined by how well outcomes meet or exceed expectations. For example, if organizational participants feel that they are working much harder than others in the same organization, but are receiving fewer rewards, they will probably have a negative attitude towards the work.
3. Job satisfaction represent several attitudes, they are:
 - a. Pay
 - b. Promotion opportunities
 - c. Working conditions
 - d. Co-worker relationship
 - e. Supervision
 - f. The work nature

NEED HIERARCHY THEORY FOR JOB SATISFACTION:

One of the most widely mentioned theories of motivation is the hierarchy of needs theory put forth by psychologist Abraham Maslow. Maslow saw human needs in the form of a hierarchy, ascending from the lowest to the highest, and he concluded that when one set of needs is satisfied, this kind of need ceases to be a motivator.

As per his theory these needs are:

Physiological needs:

These are important needs for sustaining the human life. Food, water, warmth, shelter, sleep, medicine and education are the basic physiological needs which fall in the primary list of need satisfaction. Maslow was of an opinion that until these needs were satisfied to a degree to maintain life, no other motivating factors can work.

Security or Safety needs:

These are the needs to be free of physical danger and of the fear of losing a job, property, food or shelter. It also includes protection against any emotional harm.

Social needs:

Since people are social beings, they need to belong and be accepted by others. People try to satisfy their need for affection, acceptance and friendship.

Esteem needs:

According to Maslow, once people begin to satisfy their need to belong, they tend to want to be held in esteem both by themselves and by others. This kind of need produces such satisfaction as power, prestige status and self-confidence. It includes both internal esteem factors like self-respect, autonomy and achievements and external esteem factors such as states, recognition and attention.

Need for self-actualization:

Maslow regards this as the highest need in his hierarchy. It is the drive to become what one is capable of becoming; it includes growth, achieving one's potential and self-fulfillment. It is to maximize one's potential and to accomplish something. As each of these needs is substantially satisfied, the next need becomes dominant. From the standpoint of motivation, the theory would say that although no need is ever fully gratified, a substantially satisfied need no longer motivates. So if someone wants to motivate other one, need to understand what level of the hierarchy that person is on and focus on satisfying those needs or needs above that level.

FACTORS AFFECTING JOB SATISFACTION:

There are 6 main factors influencing on Job Satisfaction clustered as physical, psychological and environmental factors as below:

Psychological Factors and Job Satisfaction:

Health and Safety:

Managing safe and healthy work environments is one of the most important environmental challenges facing organizations. Good health and safety brings more benefits that are healthy workers are more productive and can produce at a higher quality. According to Maslow "s" Hierarchy, physiological needs are the first stage in job satisfaction where as long as the work place is healthy and safe, it will create a pleasant and secure impression in employee's mind towards work.

Job Nature:

The main source of satisfaction is, of course, job itself. Researches, dedicated to job characteristics and carried out in correlation with working place projecting, testify that the very content of work and autonomy by its implementation represent two most important motivation factors correlated with labor. As research indicated, other main components of job satisfaction are interesting and difficult job without time for tedium and job giving a man one certain status. „Dealing with a workload that is far too heavy and deadlines that are impossible to reach can cause job satisfaction to erode for even the most dedicated employee. Falling short of deadlines results in conflict between employees and supervisors and raises the stress level of the workplace.

Job Security:

Job security is the assurance that a particular employee will have their job in long term due to the low probability of losing it potentially. Positive job security nature also adds more value to the image and the reputation of an organization as job offered has the guaranteed security and reliable. Also, job security has a great influence in increasing job satisfaction of its employees where once the employee is confident about not losing the job, it will create no mental stress

where the employee has its own freedom to fully concentrate on the work they perform. „An employee with a high level of job security will often performs and concentrates better than an employee who is in constant fear of losing a job. Although this fear can increase motivation in certain situations, a lack of job security can be a source of distraction and result in excess stress and low morale that hinders an employee's overall performance.

Job promotion:

Companies provide promotion to their employees considering experience, service and some companies reward promotions through measuring employee’s talents and capabilities. „give their priority to current employees to apply vacancy is arises. In that situation employees can achieve their individual goals obtaining promotion. Through such a situation, increases employee’s satisfaction and they more contribute to the productivity.

Physical Factors and Job Satisfaction:

Payment :

Money rewards are multi complex and multisided job satisfaction factor. Money not only gives people an opportunity to satisfy their primary needs, but also fosters satisfaction of higher levels needs. „Those who make more money are little more satisfied than those who make considerably less. Moreover, relatively well paid samples of individuals are only trivially more satisfied than relatively poorly paid samples.

Employees:

more often perceive their salary’s level as a reflection of that how management estimates their contribution to the company’s activity. If employees have an opportunity to choose themselves to some extend independently indulgences from the whole package rendered by the company then they receive greater satisfaction from indulgences receivables and the job in the whole.

Working groups:

Direct affect on job satisfaction makes the very nature of work groups. Working group serves for a single worker is a source of support, comfort, advice and

enjoyment from the very job. A “good” working group fosters a gaining of a greater joy and pleasure from job. On another hand, when the opposite situation is observed, when it is hard to get along with the people, the given factor imposes negative impact on job satisfaction.

Welfare Services:

Welfare includes anything that is done for the comfort and improvement of employees and is provided over and above the wages. Welfare helps in keeping the morale and motivation of the employees high so as to retain the employees for longer duration. Labor welfare includes various facilities, services and amenities provided to workers for improving their health, efficiency, economic betterment and social status.

Use of skills and abilities:

Everyone has skills and abilities. Some are unique aptitudes and talents, which may include musical abilities (singing, playing an instrument, composing music), artistic skills (drawing, painting, sculpting), athletic skills (running, jumping, throwing), or any other ability that comes easily and naturally. Some skills and abilities are used in daily work life. The company should identify which skills and abilities are available in the employee and should give opportunities for improve them.

Environmental Factors and Job Satisfaction:

Working conditions:

One more factor imposing moderate impact on job satisfaction is working conditions. If conditions are good (e.g. offices are neat and cozy, clean and engaging), staff could easier manage their job. If bad working conditions were available (e.g. it is hot or noisy in the office), it would be more difficult for employees to implement their work. Otherwise, working conditions affect job satisfaction similar to working group’s influence. If all were favorably around, there would not be problems with job satisfaction.

Management style & culture: Organizational culture :

is the organization’s pattern of beliefs, expectations, and values as in company and industry practices. A major organizational factor to which new employees must be socialized is the

culture of the group they are joining. Research Project Individual Assignment BM/N/03/17
11The potential benefits of improved job design are unlikely to be realized, if attention is focused on the content of jobs alone. Equal, if not more important, is the process by which redesign is carried out. This has led to recognition of the importance of management style and, increasingly, of organization culture. Central to improving the quality of working life is a participative, open style of management involving employees in decisions that affect them, including the design or choice of the technology itself. Personnel policies, including those related to pay and benefits, should attempt to develop a relationship of trust among all members and sections of the organization, and a confident partnership approach to trade unions.

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